

Primary Mathematics Technological Anxiety: A Mixed Methods Exploratory Case Study of Primary Pre-Service Teachers

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Using the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) survey (Koehler & Mishra, 2008) and an Abbreviated Mathematics Rating Scale (AMARS, Richardson & Suinn, 1972) to measure the Technological Knowledge and Mathematics Anxiety of 30 Postgraduate (PGCE) Primary pre-service teachers, the exploratory case study highlighted several indicators of Mathematics Technological Anxiety. Although data was collected using a variety of quantitative and qualitative measures, only the quantitative findings are initially discussed in this paper. Pre and posttest statistical analyses revealed that although pre-service teachers' mathematics anxiety levels significantly decreased by the end of the course, technological knowledge did not significantly improve. Additionally, the TPACK survey revealed that technological anxiety ensued when student teachers felt pressurized to utilize technology to improve their personal mathematics content knowledge.

Introduction

Where an abundance of studies exist on the mathematics anxiety of primary preservice primary teachers (Boyd et al., 2014), limited research is available on the technological or computer anxiety of preservice teachers (Eko Setyarini, 2018; Tatar et al., 2015). Nevertheless, although research has shown strategies to reduce mathematics anxiety (Finlayson, 2014; Sidiqi, 2017) very few of these studies refer to the use of technological interventions as methods to reduce mathematics anxiety with primary preservice teachers specifically. This case study was conducted to contribute to this body of knowledge by highlighting the impact of using iPads as tools to improve Maths Content knowledge (CK) and changing levels of pre-service teachers' Maths anxiety. This paper will discuss the quantitative findings of TPACK and Maths anxiety levels of 30 PGCE primary preservice teachers studying in Northern Ireland (NI).

Review of Literature

NI Context

In 2008, the GTCNI (General Teaching Council for Northern Ireland) investigated the numbers of teachers on its register that held one or more Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) teaching qualifications, or other academic STEM qualifications. Stewart (2014, p. 4) reported that the investigation found that, "10% of all teachers registered in Northern Ireland had a science or mathematics background and only 23% of STEM specialists worked in primary schools." This was then followed by the Report of the STEM Review (2009), where Perry (2012, p. 2) noted "a continual decline in interest in STEM subjects beginning in the latter years of primary education." Nevertheless, Hilton (2016)

found that integrating technology into the mathematics classroom helps reduce Mathematical Anxiety (MA) in students and positively influences student engagement.

Mathematical Anxiety (MA)

Introduced as *number anxiety* by Dreger and Aiken (1957), MA is defined by Dowker (2016, p. 508) as “severely disrupts...mathematical learning and performance, both by causing avoidance of mathematical activities and by overloading and disrupting working memory during mathematical tasks”. Although the study of mathematics anxiety has spanned almost sixty years, minimal research exists regarding the impact of school initiatives upon teachers’ mathematics anxiety and more specifically preservice teachers’ MA.

Barry (2017, p. 25) comments, “Technology helps take away the pressure and anxiety associated with worksheets and the traditional teaching practices in math and provide an avenue to explore and enjoy doing mathematics”. Both Heinrich (2012) and Henderson and Yeow (2012) identified Initial Teacher Education (ITE) courses as a necessary support for effective integration of tablet devices. Several studies (Hourigan & Leavy, 2017; Tatar et al., 2015) have also shown that integrating mobile technology in the mathematics classroom can have a positive effect towards reducing MA among preservice teachers. Nevertheless, Shamoon (2014, p. 2) highlighted that as “the level of mathematical anxiety is considerably higher among students within ITE programmes compared to other university students”. Therefore, the challenge for teacher educators have been to selectively utilise the most appropriate technologies which aim to enhance mathematical learning instead of hindering it.

Boyd et al. (2014) and Harper and Danne (1998) conclude that if preservice teachers are highlighted to their individual levels of maths anxiety and are taught methods to avoid transmitting their own negative dispositions within their mathematical pedagogy then this has proven to reduce mathematics anxiety. Rayner et al. (2009) more specifically highlighted the importance of preservice teachers demonstrating a proficiency in both mathematical procedures and concepts to decrease maths anxiety levels. Sloan, (2010) & Furner & Berman, (2003) agreed that conceptual understanding, should be explored by creating environments which are student-centred and encourage the use of mathematical manipulatives which place an emphasis on sharing multiple processes and methods to help decrease anxiety. Flipped classrooms have been used to promote more student-centred opportunities during university teacher education classes.

iPad Use Within I.T.E Mathematics Teaching and Learning

Clarke and Luckin (2013, p. 11) described the iPad as ‘*a powerful, portable, personal learning partner,*’ which was fast becoming the essential toolbox for the 21st century classroom. Mango (2015) after surveying pre-service teachers use of iPads reported overwhelmingly that learning was more enjoyable, and they were able to remain more focused on classroom tasks when using iPads. Maich & Hall (2016, p. 23) concur stating, ‘*iPads can improve classroom learning.*’ Walter (2011) reported many advantages of iPads including; allowing a smooth transition from software-specific projects with a steep learning curve to smaller scale apps-based learning tasks, ease of use with apps instead of software

training, as well as portability and kinaesthetic interactions that traditional desktop or laptop computers could not offer. Indeed, Clarke and Luckin (2013) have highlighted various models and strategies for iPad implementation used throughout schools both nationwide and internationally and it is clear from practitioner blogs (Andrews, 2013; Page Burdick, 2013; Swanson, 2013) that although overall teachers’ perceptions on iPad use enhanced their learners’ experience and transformed their pedagogical style. Cheu-Jay (2015) indicated that mathematical classroom success was more attributable to the fact that teachers who integrated iPads into their lessons tended to do more Project Based Learning (PBL), which had a profound improvement to student learning across grade levels. Baran (2014, p. 17) lists six key research findings in her review of mobile learning in Teacher Education, concluding with the finding that several pedagogical affordances support mobile learning integration into teacher education settings. Nonetheless, although some UK iPad research exists, many studies (Burden et. al, 2012; Heinrich, 2012; Hopkins & Burden, 2014) indicate that there remains “the need for further research in the area of educational use of iPads for both pre- and in-service teachers in addition to how attitudes towards technology affect classroom integration” (Tohill, 2014, p. 113).

Ulster University’s PGCE Primary use of Technology

The use of technology within the teaching content of the PGCE Primary provision is correlated directly to the emerging technologies utilized in NI’s Primary schools. A wide range of mobile and static devices are utilized, and student teachers effectively and selectively integrate pedagogical software and hardware within the NI Curriculum. With the introduction of iPads, an evaluation of how the devices were being implemented was prompted and the use of a mathematical TPACK survey initiated the findings.

Theoretical Framework

The TPACK framework (Koehler & Mishra, 2008) focused upon the interdependence of Technological Knowledge (TK), Pedagogical Knowledge (PK) and Content Knowledge (CK) to ‘integrate the use of digital tools and resources effectively in curriculum-based teaching.’ (Harris et al., 2017, p. i). Benton-Borghi (2013) highlight that the intricate linkage between TK, PK and CK is evidently embedded in most Initial Teacher Educational thinking.

Figure 1

TPACK framework (<http://tpack.org>)

Methodology

Research Questions

1. Did the effective use of iPad technology decrease mathematics anxiety among primary pre-service teachers?
2. Does iPad technological knowledge (TK) increase student teachers' mathematical content knowledge (CK)?
3. Is there a correlation between mathematical anxiety and mathematical content knowledge of PGCE preservice teachers?

30 PGCE Primary pre-service teachers: ten male and twenty females studying in Ulster University. Although the case study initially began with 33 participants, the attrition rate resulted in three students withdrawing before the end of the study.

Instruments

Table 1

Data Collection Tools

<i>Quantitative Collection Tools</i>	<i>Data Collection Date</i>
<i>TPACK survey (Koehler & Mishra, 2008).</i>	<i>August 2016</i>
<i>A seven-point Likert-type scale</i>	<i>June 2017</i>
<i>AMARS (Richardson and Suinn, 2012).</i>	<i>August 2016</i>
<i>25 statements - 5-point Likert scale</i>	<i>June 2017</i>

Following the approval of Ulster University's Ethics Committee, the study began with the distribution of Mathematics TPACK surveys and Mathematics Anxiety Tests (AMARS) to all participants at the beginning of the PGCE Primary course (pre-test) and at the end (post-test). All steps to conceal the identity of the participants were taken. Voluntary informed consent was obtained from the participants. The researchers took all the necessary steps to ensure all participants are aware of the confidentiality of any information provided. Each participant completed a biographical profile survey which was complied with the legal requirements in relation to the storage and use of personal data as set down by the Data Protection Act (1998). To ensure anonymity of responses, each student was randomly allocated an identifier number to match up to the biographical profile survey.

Results

Research question one: Did the effective use of iPad technology decrease mathematics anxiety among primary pre-service teachers?

The quantitative analyses of the Abbreviated Mathematics Rating Scale (AMARS, 2012) revealed a highly significantly reduction to PGCE Preservice teachers' Mathematics Anxiety (MA) levels by the end of the PGCE primary course. Table 2 illustrates the Paired Sample T-Test statistical significance with gender split. MA levels were highly significantly reduced for females by the end of the PGCE course although both genders showed a significant decrease.

Table 2*Paired Samples T-Test of AMARS*

Gender		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df	Sig (2-tailed)
					Lower	Upper			
Male	AMARSpre TOT - AMARSpost TOT	14.33333	14.96663	4.98888	2.82896	25.83770	2.873	9	.021
Female	AMARSpre TOT - AMARSpost TOT	15.80000	19.45467	4.35020	6.69493	24.90507	3.632	19	.002

Research question two: Does iPad technological knowledge (TK) increase student teachers' mathematical content knowledge (CK)?

Within the TPACK survey explored student teachers' perceptions of Maths CK. Table 3 demonstrates the t-test conducted between the pre and post CK means and it is also split by gender. The results in Table 3 indicate that male student teachers perceived their Maths CK to slightly improve with $P=0.164$. Whereas for female student teachers $P=0.002$ highlighting that a highly significant improvement was made to their Mathematics CK.

Table 3*Paired Samples T-Test on Maths Content Knowledge*

Gender		Mean	Std. Deviation	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Male	preCKTOT - postCKTOT	-2.20000	4.58984	-1.516	9	.164
Female	preCKTOT - postCKTOT	-2.95000	3.77631	-3.494	19	.002

The crosstabulation results of the pre and post CK variable descriptives are outlined in Table 4 below. This was highlighted to identify the specific variables of Maths CK that held the highest significance. A significance difference was highlighted between the Pre-CK Question 1 (PVM=4.40, SD=1.102) and Post C K Question 1 (PTVM=5.73, SD=0.944); $t(29) = -5.884$, $P=0.000$. This drew the conclusion that PGCE student teachers felt that they had a wider and deeper understanding of various Maths concepts they planned to teach by the end of the course. Also, there was a higher significance difference between the Pre-CK Question 5 (PVM=5.27, SD=0.785) and Post C K Question 5 (PTVM=5.80, SD=0.714); $t(29) = -3.764$, $P=0.00$. This concluded that student teachers felt better equipped by the end of the course to have various methods and strategies which developed their mathematical understanding. Therefore, when the overall means of the CK totals were calculated $P=0.001$, this showed a highly significant improvement to CK between pre and post TPACK surveys.

Table 4*Descriptive Variables of Maths CK within the TPACK survey*

<i>Descriptive Variables</i>	Pre Var Mean	Post Var Mean	N	Pre Var SD	Post Var SD	Sig. (2- tailed)
1. I have a wide and deep understanding of the subjects I plan to teach.	4.40	5.73	30	1.102	0.944	0.000
2. I know about various examples of how mathematics applies in the real world.	5.43	5.83	30	0.898	0.34	0.056
3. I have sufficient knowledge about mathematics.	5.60	5.70	30	0.675	0.915	0.610
4. I can use a mathematical way of thinking.	5.37	5.70	30	0.999	0.877	0.057
5. I have various ways and strategies of developing my understanding of mathematics.	5.27	5.80	30	0.785	0.714	0.001

When analyzing TK exclusively within the TPACK survey, no significant difference was found in the paired sample T-Test even when the means were split by gender. $T(29) = -1.601$, $P = 0.120$. Therefore, in order to gain a further insight into why there was no significant TK improvement, a crosstabulation between the descriptive variables showed that only two TK statements held some significance. As Table 5 illustrates, these findings indicated that although PGCE student teachers learned technology more easily by the end of the course and knew more about different technologies, no overall significant difference was found to their TK.

Table 5*Descriptive Variables of Technological Knowledge within the TPACK survey*

<i>Technological Knowledge</i>	Pre Var Mean	Post Var Mean	N	Pre Var SD	Post Var SD	Sig. (2- tailed)
I know how to solve my own technical problems.	5.23	5.60	30	1.135	1.003	.094
I can learn technology easily.	5.73	6.07	30	0.521	0.640	.005
I keep up with important new technologies.	5.27	5.47	30	0.868	0.973	.339
I frequently play around with the technology.	5.10	5.30	30	0.995	1.368	.476
I know about a lot of different technologies.	4.20	5.00	30	1.126	1.203	.006
I have the technical skills I need to use technology.	5.57	5.57	30	1.203	0.774	1.000
I have sufficient opportunities to work with different technologies.	5.47	5.43	30	1.008	1.194	.897
When I encounter a problem using technology, I seek outside help.	4.87	4.77	30	1.507	1.478	.775

Therefore, it was non-conclusive that the improvements to CK could have been attributed to TK. As the improvement to TPACK was highly significant $P=0.000$, the T-Tests listed in table 6 show that TK was the only element of TPACK that didn't improve significantly. Table 6 highlights the need for qualitative data to explore in greater depth the qualitative reasons why student teachers' TK did not significantly improve. Hence, the quantitative data was non-conclusive if the improvements to Mathematics CK was attributed to TK.

Table 6*Paired Samples T-Tests for all seven TPACK domains.*

TPACK VARIABLES	P- VALUES
TKTOT	P = 0.120
CKTOT	P = 0.001
PKTOT	P = 0.000
PCKTOT	P = 0.000
TCKTOT	P = 0.018
TPKTOT	P = 0.000
TPACKTOT	P = 0.000

Research Question Three: Is there a correlation between MA levels and Maths CK?

Linear regression was used to ascertain if there was a correlation MA levels and Maths CK. The dependent variable in this case was MA with CK from the TPACK survey as the independent variable. The overall idea of using regression was to examine whether there was a correlation between MA levels and doing a maths test. The result showed a positive correlation with $Y = 0.675$.

Discussion and Recommendations

To conclude, quantitative results showed that PGCE student teachers' Maths CK significantly improve and MA levels also significantly decreased by the end of the course, however, TK did not improve. The findings showed that the use of iPads specifically, was not a medium by which student teachers felt comfortable implementing to improve their Maths CK. The TPACK survey did highlight that if iPads were implemented in mathematical teaching and learning in a scaffolded constructivist way, incorporating peer collaborative shared learning, then this pedagogic approach could be more impactful within Initial Teacher Education (ITE) programmes.

Despite the TPACK survey indicating that TK remained unimproved, qualitative data is required to explore why this was so. It is likely however, that due to the changing nature of our digital world and the evolution of TK, it is unlikely that PGCE student teachers would acquire all the TK necessary and the need for Continuous Professional Development (CPD) of new technologies is essential in order to have a fuller understanding of the affordances of technologies effectively implemented within mathematical teaching and learning. Currently, the GTCNI has no stipulated CPD requirement for qualified teachers, whereas in Scotland, the GTC requires a minimum of 35 hours per year of CPD. Although the monitoring of this CPD requirement has been questioned (Kennedy et al., 2008), the benefit to the effectiveness of ICT pedagogical practices in Scottish primary mathematical education is outweighed (Burden et al., 2012).

Limitations

The limitations to this study was the small sample size of the PGCE cohort involved and it would be an interesting further study to make comparisons of mathematical and technological knowledge of other PGCE primary cohorts in the UK mainland. Additionally, as this paper explored quantitative findings exclusively, it would be interesting to follow this with some qualitative findings which would substantiate the differential statistics found.

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